

MIAU: An analysis-ready dataset on presence-only and presence-absence data of Neotropical carnivores (Mammalia, Carnivora) from 2000 to 2021

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Abstract

In the last decade, databases of records of species observed at the same location at different points in time over large spatial extents have been made available. Unfortunately, these sources are scarce in regions such as Latin America. We present a dataset of 60,179 point occurrences (i.e. presence-only data, PO) and 45,468 camera-trap survey records (i.e. presence-absence data, PA) for 63 species of carnivores of the Neotropical Region from 2000 to 2021. We collated the data from various sources, including 64 newly-digitised bibliographic references. We cleaned, taxonomically harmonised and standardised the data following the Darwin Core and Humboldt Core standards and present them here as csv files. We have also made these data fit for analyses by aggregating the data into two time periods (time1: 2000–2013 and time2: 2014–2021), with PO grid cell counts of 100 × 100 km and PA polygons of varying size, presented as geopackage files. These data can be used for large-scale species distribution models, calculation of population trends, extinction risk analyses and educational purposes.

Key words: Camera trap, data deficiency, Latin America, point occurrence, species distribution models

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Introduction

To understand and monitor global biodiversity change over time, we need data on species distributions spanning long time periods and large spatial areas (Yoccoz et al. 2001; Schmeller et al. 2017; Wüest et al. 2020). In the last decade, several databases holding these types of data have been developed. For example, BioTIME (Dornelas et al. 2018), the Living Planet Index (WWF 2022) and Breeding Birds Surveys from North America (Ziolkowski et al. 2022) or the UK (Heywood et al. 2024). Unfortunately, these sources are mostly biased towards Europe and the US, while they are practically non-existent in regions such as Latin America (Meyer et al. 2016).

To study changes in the distribution of continental-wide species in such data-scarce areas, there are two options. First, we can gather data from scratch, but this is challenging at large scales. Alternatively, we can rescue and collate multiple already-published sources and digitise, clean, harmonise and

standardise them for reuse (Griffin 2015). This is the approach we followed to study the range dynamics of Neotropical carnivores. With the data, we first assessed the temporal change in the geographic distribution of the jaguarundi, *Herpailurus yagouaroundi*, through a novel modelling approach that integrates presence-only and presence-absence data (Grattarola et al. 2023). Later, we used similar data for modelling multiple carnivore species and calculated hotspots of change, i.e. areas where range contractions and expansions are accumulating more (Grattarola et al. 2024). The data we gathered can also be used for different new purposes.

An important lesson from these analyses and also from other authors (e.g. Elith et al. 2020) is the value of having different types of data systematically revised and accessible, particularly with presence-only and presence-absence data organised in a way that allows them to be used together effectively. This is important, particularly in relatively under-studied regions where each of the data is relatively scarce, but together they form a basis for robust analyses; specifically, the presence-only data provide better geographical coverage, while the presence-absence data can be used to calibrate predictions to a probability scale (Guillera-Arroita et al. 2015). Another (painful) lesson is how much time one must spend on the process of gathering, cleaning and preparing the data for the purpose of statistical analyses. We believe that the scientific community would benefit from having access to a dataset that has already undergone such treatment.

Here, we present MIAU, a ready-to-use, cleaned, continental-wide dataset on presences-only and presences-absences of Neotropical carnivores. We expect the dataset to be useful for many purposes, such as large-scale species distribution models, calculation of population trends and extinction risk analyses, ultimately providing information for large-scale conservation of one of the most charismatic taxonomic groups in the Neotropics.

Methods

We compiled data from different sources (Table 1), for 63 species of carnivores from the Neotropical Region (Table 2). We included records from the GBIF database (GBIF.org 2024), records extracted from a data paper (Nagy-Reis et al. 2020) and from 64 digitised literature sources (see Suppl. material 1 for a complete list). This last is one of the most important contributions of our dataset. We have mobilised 10,684 records from literature and made them publicly available here for the first time. We cleaned, taxonomically harmonised (according to Mammal Diversity Database 2022) and standardised all records following the Darwin Core (<https://dwc.tdwg.org/>; Wieczorek et al. 2012) and Humboldt

Table 1. Data sources in our dataset, including the source type, number of datasets involved, data type, number of species and number of records they span.

Source	Source type	Datasets involved	Data type	Number of species	Number of records
GBIF.org (2024)	online database	434	presence-only	59	56,413
Nagy-Reis et al. (2020)	data paper	105	presence-only	31	3,766
Nagy-Reis et al. (2020)	data paper	207	presence-absence	45	34,784
Literature sources processed in this study (Suppl. material 1)	literature	64	presence-absence	40	10,684

Table 2. List of species covered by our dataset, including family and the number of presence-only (PO) and presence-absence (PA) records (only reported presences).

Species	Family	Number of PO records	Number of PA records
<i>Atelocynus microtis</i>	Canidae	41	290
<i>Canis latrans</i>	Canidae	2288	89
<i>Canis lupus</i>	Canidae	241	0
<i>Cerdocyon thous</i>	Canidae	4332	4065
<i>Chrysocyon brachyurus</i>	Canidae	575	480
<i>Lycalopex culpaeus</i>	Canidae	8561	41
<i>Lycalopex fulvipes</i>	Canidae	72	0
<i>Lycalopex grisea</i>	Canidae	80	11
<i>Lycalopex gymnocerca</i>	Canidae	2087	508
<i>Lycalopex sechurae</i>	Canidae	13	34
<i>Lycalopex vetula</i>	Canidae	91	127
<i>Speothos venaticus</i>	Canidae	60	64
<i>Urocyon cinereoargenteus</i>	Canidae	2868	204
<i>Vulpes macrotis</i>	Canidae	132	0
<i>Herpailurus yagouaroundi</i>	Felidae	1171	787
<i>Leopardus colocola</i>	Felidae	183	1
<i>Leopardus geoffroyi</i>	Felidae	302	249
<i>Leopardus guigna</i>	Felidae	509	6
<i>Leopardus guttulus</i>	Felidae	34	742
<i>Leopardus jacobitus</i>	Felidae	1	0
<i>Leopardus pajeros</i>	Felidae	8	0
<i>Leopardus pardalis</i>	Felidae	3371	4242
<i>Leopardus tigrinus</i>	Felidae	379	224
<i>Leopardus wiedii</i>	Felidae	471	918
<i>Lynx rufus</i>	Felidae	1055	56
<i>Panthera onca</i>	Felidae	1230	2074
<i>Puma concolor</i>	Felidae	3999	2478
<i>Conepatus chinga</i>	Mephitidae	629	189
<i>Conepatus leuconotus</i>	Mephitidae	406	71
<i>Conepatus semistriatus</i>	Mephitidae	578	380
<i>Mephitis macroura</i>	Mephitidae	569	28
<i>Mephitis mephitis</i>	Mephitidae	210	0
<i>Spilogale angustifrons</i>	Mephitidae	161	6
<i>Spilogale gracilis</i>	Mephitidae	106	11
<i>Spilogale pygmaea</i>	Mephitidae	16	3
<i>Eira barbara</i>	Mustelidae	2957	2223
<i>Galictis cuja</i>	Mustelidae	374	101
<i>Galictis vittata</i>	Mustelidae	196	44
<i>Lontra canadensis</i>	Mustelidae	1	0
<i>Lontra longicaudis</i>	Mustelidae	959	86
<i>Lontra provocax</i>	Mustelidae	81	1
<i>Neogale felipei</i>	Mustelidae	1	0
<i>Neogale frenata</i>	Mustelidae	251	26
<i>Pteronura brasiliensis</i>	Mustelidae	272	22
<i>Taxidea taxus</i>	Mustelidae	154	0
<i>Bassaricyon alleni</i>	Procyonidae	32	1
<i>Bassaricyon gabbii</i>	Procyonidae	53	0
<i>Bassaricyon medius</i>	Procyonidae	11	0
<i>Bassaricyon neblina</i>	Procyonidae	26	0
<i>Bassariscus astutus</i>	Procyonidae	1113	40
<i>Bassariscus sumichrasti</i>	Procyonidae	63	1

Species	Family	Number of PO records	Number of PA records
<i>Nasua narica</i>	Procyonidae	5127	303
<i>Nasua nasua</i>	Procyonidae	2620	2908
<i>Nasua olivacea</i>	Procyonidae	275	3
<i>Potos flavus</i>	Procyonidae	815	17
<i>Procyon cancrivorus</i>	Procyonidae	2681	1661
<i>Procyon lotor</i>	Procyonidae	2098	120
<i>Procyon pygmaeus</i>	Procyonidae	1	0
<i>Tremarctos ornatus</i>	Ursidae	2753	26
<i>Ursus americanus</i>	Ursidae	436	22

Core (<https://eco.tdwg.org/>; Guralnick et al. 2018) standards. For a complete list of columns/terms and definitions, see the metadata files ('Data availability: underlying data'). In total, our dataset contains 105,647 records (Table 1). The data and code used to process the data of this manuscript can be accessed at <https://github.com/bienflores/MIAU> (Grattarola et al. 2024).

This dataset was generated to study the range dynamics of eight Neotropical carnivores (Grattarola et al. 2023, 2024).

Presence-absence (PA) data

We extracted the PA data from two main data sources. The first was the database of Nagy-Reis et al. (2020) (207 surveys). The second was our own manual extraction of data from primary published sources such as camera-trap surveys (64 surveys). Details on both data sources follow:

The Nagy-Reis et al. (2020) database of Neotropical carnivores collates records from different heterogeneous sources (e.g. researchers, governmental agencies, non-governmental organisations and private consultants) and methods (e.g. camera trapping, museum collections, roadkill, line transect and opportunistic records). From this database, we kept the data generated by surveys using camera traps (with detection and non-detection values), geographic coordinates, information about the study sampling area, with starting and ending month and year of the study and reported sampling effort (i.e. the number of active camera-trap days). We calculated 'temporalSpan' as the difference in days from 'end date of the study - start date of the study', assuming that the studies started the first day of the month and ended the last day of the month, as the start and end day were not recorded in the data. We considered the size of the study area as either the reported area for studies at the level of 'UNIT' or the latitude/longitude precision in metres for the studies at the sampling level of 'AREA' (see the metadata in Nagy-Reis et al. (2020) for more details on these definitions). Finally, we standardised column names and harmonised the taxonomy.

For the literature data extraction, we explored 262 potential sources and kept 64 (see 'Data availability: source data') that included studies in the Neotropics using camera traps that were performed from the 2000s onwards, reported all surveyed species and stated the sampling effort and the study area. We excluded studies that were exclusively focused on arboreal species, reported only some focal species and discarded others, and used a combination of sampling methods for which the effort in camera-trap days to detect a species was not possible to extract or calculate. We excluded further 22 studies for being duplicated sources and did not digitise 18 studies that were located in areas where

we already had sufficient data. For all studies, we report the presence/absence of the species under 'presence'. For those that included an abundance metric, we report it under the 'abundance' column and report the abundance units used in 'abundanceUnits' (e.g. NOIR: number of individual records, RAI: relative abundance index - number of records per trap effort, AI/month: abundance index per month). Digitisation of the literature data represented a huge challenge as the different sources reported the spatial information, sampling effort and sampling period of the studies in very heterogeneous and incomplete ways and many times, they did not provide the primary data, but aggregated information. Therefore, as we often had to estimate or calculate these values, we report the origin of the information about effort, area of study and time span in specific columns. The column 'areaOrigin' refers to whether the area was given in the article, estimated from information provided in the article or calculated by manually georeferencing the study area or extracting the information from WDPA (UNEP-WCMC 2022) if it was a protected area. When the coordinates of individual camera traps were available, but no study area was provided, we considered the area as 10 m² (circle with a radius of 1.784 m) per camera (i.e. the estimated effective area of a camera). When the survey area was provided as a transect (either mentioning the centroid and length or with a map), we estimated the study area as 'transect length * 3.568 m' (diameter of effective camera trap area). The column 'effortOrigin' refers to whether the sampling effort was given in the article or calculated from the information provided. When the effort was not given, we calculated it either by multiplying the 'number of camera traps' by the 'sampling effort in days' for each individual camera or as the 'number of camera traps' by the 'temporal span in days', depending on which information was provided in the article. The column 'temporalSpanOrigin' refers to whether the temporal span of the study was either given in the article or calculated (as 'end date of the study - start date of the study').

Presence-only (PO) data

We extracted the PO data from two main data sources, the GBIF's (2024) database (56,413 records) and the Nagy-Reis et al.'s (2020) database (3,766 records). Details follow:

We extracted occurrence records from the GBIF database (GBIF.org 2024), the largest open data aggregator of primary biodiversity data. We downloaded all records available for the 71 species in the Neotropics using 'rgbif' (Chamberlain et al. 2024), considering records with geographic coordinates and no spatial issues, that were not fossil records nor living specimens and which establishment means was not managed, introduced, naturalised or invasive. These data were then further cleaned by removing records with coordinate uncertainty greater than 25,000 metres and filtering those records that belonged to *Canis lupus familiaris* or *Canis familiaris* (domestic dog). We also used 'CoordinateCleaner' (Zizka et al. 2019) to remove records within 2 kilometres of country and capital centroids (i.e. a common georeference generalisation), within 2 km of zoo and herbaria and records that fell outside the landmass and outliers (i.e. records located more than 1000 km to all other records of a species). Finally, we discarded duplicates considering independent records as species recorded on different dates and latitude and longitude coordinates.

For the records that had a sampling period as the collection/observation date, we considered the first day of the survey as the event date. From the total 209,277 records downloaded we ended up keeping 56,413 (27%). The largest exclusion of records was done when considering duplicates, yet many records also lacked critical information in terms of taxon, time and location (Peterson et al. 2018). The largest data provider of the final data is the iNaturalist citizen-science platform (47.1%).

We complemented the GBIF data with records from the Nagy-Reis et al. (2020) database. We kept records that reported count data (i.e. not data on detection/non-detections) and that had been collected using one of the following methods: 'line transect', 'active searching', 'roadkill', 'museum', 'opportunistic'. As the day of the event date was not stated for these data, we considered the 1st of the month to be the day of the event and discarded those that did not have an event date. Finally, we removed duplicates considering independent records as species recorded on different dates and latitude and longitude coordinates.

Analysis-ready data

The main goal of creating this analysis-ready data was to use it in the studies Grattarola et al. (2023, 2024) to model the temporal dynamics of the carnivores in the Neotropics (i.e. how their geographic ranges vary over time). With this purpose, we generated a dataset for each data type (PO and PA) (Table 3) based on different spatial features (i.e. grid cells of presence-only counts and presence-absence polygons) (Fig. 1) and splitting the data into two time periods, time1: 2000–2013 and time2: 2014–2021. This temporal division was the minimum possible to run our statistical models efficiently, given the low number of data points we had for some species, but it was also chosen to be able to represent, on average, 50% of the data in each period for our temporal change analyses. See more details in Grattarola et al. (2023) and Grattarola et al. (2024).

The PO data consist of 100 × 100 km grid cells with counts for each species in the two time periods. We provide the code to generate the grid-cells, which can be adapted to any other preferred size and temporal extension.

The PA data consists of polygons of varying sizes of aggregated camera-trap studies per time period. To create them, we generated a buffer polygon for each survey using the latitude and longitude of the survey as centroid and the study area as buffer. Then, all overlapping polygons were combined and absences were generated for each species in those polygons where the species was not recorded. For each polygon at each time period, we calculated the total surface area, timespan and the effort in camera-trap days and the aggregated presence for each species. We also provide the code to generate the polygons to split the data at any other preferred temporal split (e.g. biannual or every five years).

Table 3. Summary of the analysis-ready data, including the data type, spatial features and spatial and temporal resolution.

Data type	Spatial features	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution
Presence-only (PO)	2,265 grid cells with counts per species	100 × 100 km	2 time periods (2000 to 2013 and 2014 to 2021)
Presence-absence (PA)	565 polygons of presences/absences values per each species	Varying sizes	2 time periods (2000 to 2013 and 2014 to 2021)

Figure 1. Spatial features (geometries) of the analysis-ready **a** presence-only (100 × 100 km grid cells) and **b** presence-absence data (aggregated polygons of varying sizes). PA polygons were buffered by 20 km to improve visibility.

Dataset coverage and limitations

Geographic coverage

The data cover the entire Neotropical Region, spanning 26 countries from Central to South America (Fig. 2). For the presence-only data, the country with the highest number of records is Mexico ($n = 15,409$), followed by Colombia ($n = 12,780$) and Chile ($n = 10,632$), while the countries with the least number of records are Venezuela ($n = 31$) and Guyana ($n = 29$). If we consider the density of records per area, then Costa Rica is the best-covered country (58.6 records / $1,000$ km²), followed by Chile (15.6 records / $1,000$ km²), while the poorest covered country is Venezuela (0.04 records / $1,000$ km²) (Suppl. material 2). In the case of the presence-absence data, the country with the most records is Brazil ($n = 17,341$ detected presences), followed by Bolivia ($n = 1,858$) and Argentina ($n = 1,365$), while those with the least number of detected presences are Honduras and Belize ($n = 5$ each). Considering the density of surveys per area, then again, Costa Rica is the best-covered country (0.157 surveys / $1,000$ km²), while Venezuela and Chile are the worst-covered (0.001 surveys / $1,000$ km²) (Suppl. material 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of the **a** presence-only (PO) occurrence records ($n = 60,179$) and **b** presence-absence (PA) surveys ($n = 271$) of carnivore species from the Neotropics.

Taxonomic coverage

The dataset includes a total of 63 species of carnivores native to the Neotropics (Fig. 3); the PO data spans 60 species, while the PA data includes 49 species. Species names were harmonised to follow the Mammal Diversity Database of the American Society of Mammalogists (Mammal Diversity Database 2022). According to this database, there are 71 carnivore species in the region (12 Canidae, 13 Felidae, 3 Mephitidae, 6 Mustelidae, 8 Procyonidae and 1 Ursidae); thus, our dataset spans 88.7% of the species recorded in the Neotropics (Table 2).

The following species are not included in our dataset: *Leopardus braccatus*, *L. fasciatus* and *L. garleppi* (from the *Leopardus colocola* complex), *L. narinensis* and *L. emiliae* (from the *Leopardus tigrinus* complex), *Spilogale interrupta*, *S. leucoparia* and *S. yucatanensis* and *Enhydra lutris*. The following species are poorly covered by our dataset (only a few records are included): *Leopardus pajeros* and *L. colocola* (from the *Leopardus colocola* complex), *Leopardus jacobita*, *Lyncodon patagonicus*, *Lontra canadensis*, *Neogale felipei* and *N. africana*. This is because most of these species are distributed either in Mexico or Argentina (northern and southernmost countries of the Neotropics) and they are not exclusive to the Neotropics or abundant in this region. Other species, such as those in the pampas cat (*Leopardus colocola*) species complex and the tiger cat (*Leopardus tigrinus*) species complex, have gone through several recent taxonomic changes and rediscoveries (Nascimento et al. 2020; Astorquiza et al. 2023; Lescroart et al. 2023) that make the correct assignment of the geographic distribution of each record a challenge.

Figure 3. Number of records (a) and species (b) for the presence-only (PO) data and number of records (c) and species (d) for the presence-absence (PA) data in our dataset. Shown in greyscale are the carnivores' family.

Temporal coverage

The data have been observed from 01-01-2000 to 31-12-2021, with a more intense effort over the last five years (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Number of (a) presence-only (PO) and (b) presence-absence (PA) records of carnivore species from the Neotropics over the years. For the PA data, the start and end of the survey is displayed as a segment. Shown in greyscale are the carnivores' family.

Limitations

Geographic

Some countries are poorly covered in our dataset (i.e. have fewer records than expected), while others are well-covered (Fig. 1, Suppl. material 2). These differences mostly arise because countries in Latin America have different

data-sharing capacities (with Brazil and Colombia at the top, De Vega et al. 2020; Soberón 2022) and citizen-science levels of participation (Ortega-Álvarez and Casas 2022), yet the disparity does not necessarily reflect real differences in species richness or abundance per country. Due to this, but also because of the limited access to some areas of the continent, certain regions/biomes are likewise unevenly covered by our dataset (e.g. Amazon, Fig. 2). Thus, we recommend data users be cautious and account for this uneven sampling effort between countries and regions when using the data. An example of how to account for this is what we did in Grattarola et al. (2023) and Grattarola et al. (2024). We expected that highly accessible grid cells would have more point records than inaccessible grid cells and that differences would also vary amongst countries. Thus, we included the country of origin of the record and the degree of accessibility to the area in the observation process of our integrated species distribution model. If accounting for sampling bias is unfeasible, users could exclude sites with sampling effort below a set threshold to ensure adequate coverage for posterior analyses. However, how to address data gaps will depend on the specific research question (Bowler et al. 2024).

Temporal

Most PO records come from the second time period. This is characteristic of the data made available on GBIF (i.e. an artefact) and not a real difference in species abundance over time. In Grattarola et al. (2024), we found that the number of records between 2000–2013 and 2014–2021, using all the data available in GBIF for the eight studied species, was on average 27% higher in the second period. Thus, we recommend data users be cautious and account for this increasing sampling effort over the years. An example can be to include the ratio of the number of records between periods in the model, as we did in Grattarola et al. (2024). More solutions for data gaps can be explored at Bowler et al. (2024).

Taxonomic

Although we cover 87.7% of the species recorded in Neotropical countries (63 out of 71), for those species that are not exclusively distributed there (i.e. they are primarily distributed in the Nearctic Region, Mammal Diversity Database 2022), the data may not be representative of their entire distribution, but only their distribution in this region. Thus, for the following species, we caution users to consider our data insufficient for single species distribution analyses: *Canis latrans*, *Canis lupus*, *Vulpes macrotis*, *Lynx rufus*, *Puma concolor*, *Conepatus leuconotus*, *Mephitis macroura*, *M. mephitis*, *Enhydra lutris*, *Spilogale angustifrons*, *S. gracilis*, *S. interrupta*, *S. leucoparia*, *S. pygmaea*, *Lontra canadensis*, *Taxidea taxus*, *Bassariscus astutus*, *Procyon lotor* and *Ursus americanus*. Many of the studies we digitised from literature were conducted in forest habitats; thus, grassland and riverine species (such as *Lycalopex gymnocerca* and *Lontra longicaudis*) may also be under-represented in our data. For several rare species, our dataset has very few records; thus, the same previous reasoning applies. These are: *Procyon pygmaeus* and *Spilogale pygmaea* endemic from Mexico, *Lycalopex vetula* and *Leopardus emiliae* endemic from Brazil, *Lycalopex fulvipes*

and *Leopardus colocola* endemic from Chile and *Leopardus narinensis* endemic from Colombia. Despite we collated the literature data following the same strategy with which we filtered the Nagy-Reis data paper, in the case of the literature data, we also did not consider data that only reported a few species from the total found in the survey (e.g. only the jaguar was reported). As we could not know the taxonomic scope of the surveys in the Nagy-Reis data paper, an unintended bias could arise from this.

Future directions

As the project has ended, we do not plan to update the dataset soon. However, with our data structure description, detailed data cleaning and standardisation workflow and code available, we encourage future users to update the dataset as needed.

Data availability

1) Source data: the downloaded/digitised data sources

- 64 literature sources. See the files 'literature_all_references.ods' for a complete list and 'literature_digitised_references.bib' for the BibTeX bibliographical database. See also Suppl. material 1.
- GBIF.org. (2024). 'Occurrence Download Neotropical Carnivores'. <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.67zvau>.
- Nagy-Reis et al. (2020). 'NEOTROPICAL CARNIVORES: A Data Set on Carnivore Distribution in the Neotropics'. *Ecology* 101(11): e03128. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.3128>.

2) Underlying data: the data we generated

Tables

- `data_PO.csv`: a csv file with the cleaned, standardised and harmonised presence-only data.
- `metadata_PO.csv`: a csv file with the column names, standard terms (e.g. Darwin Core or Humboldt Core) and definitions for the presence-only data.
- `data_PA.csv`: a csv file with the cleaned, standardised and harmonised presence-absence data.
- `metadata_PA.csv`: a csv file with the column names, standard terms (e.g. Darwin Core or Humboldt Core) and definitions for the presence-absence data.
- `carnivores.csv`: a csv file with the carnivore species' list extracted from the Mammal Diversity Database (2022), including the family, taxon key from GBIF and IUCN conservation status.

Spatial files

- `PO.gpk`: a geopackage with 2 layers; `time1`: a multi polygon sf file with 2,265 grid cells of 100 × 100 km resolution with counts per species

in the temporal period from 2000 to 2013 and `time2`: a multi polygon sf file with 2,265 grid cells of 100 × 100 km resolution with counts per species in the temporal period from 2014 to 2021. Projection: Lambert azimuthal equal-area projection; centre latitude 0°S and centre longitude 73.125°W.

- `PA.gpk`: a geopackage with 2 layers; `time1`: a multi polygon sf file with 565 varying size polygons of presences/absences values for each species, area of the polygon and sampling effort in days in the temporal period from 2000 to 2013 and `time2`: a multi polygon sf file with 1013 varying size polygons of presences/absences for each species in the temporal period from 2014 to 2021, with the area of the polygon and sampling effort in days. Projection: Lambert azimuthal equal-area projection; centre latitude 0°S and centre longitude 73.125°W.
- `latam.gpk`: a geopackage with 4 layers; `countries`: a multi polygon sf file for all 27 Latin American countries, `countries_land` a multi polygon sf file for the 21 landmass countries of Latin America (excluding islands), `latam` a single polygon that combines all the landmass countries of Latin America and `latam_grids` a multi polygon sf file with 2,265 grid cells of 100 × 100 km resolution and `latam` as extension. Projection: Lambert azimuthal equal-area projection; centre latitude 0°S and centre longitude 73.125°W.

Other files

- `literature_digitised_references.bib`: BibTeX bibliographical database file with the 64 literature references digitised and included in our database.
- `literature_digitised_references.csv`: a csv file with the 64 literature references digitised and included in our database (see also Suppl. material 1).
- `literature_all_references.ods`: an open-source spreadsheet file with literature references (title and DOI or URL) including 4 sheets; `articles_EXCLUDED` articles that did not fulfil our assumptions and were excluded (reasons are reported in the column notes), `articles_DUPLICATED`: articles that were found in the reference lists of other datasets already digitised (e.g. Nagy-Reis et al. 2020), `articles_DIGITISED` articles that were digitised and included in the data and `articles_TO_PROCESS`: articles that fulfil our assumptions, but were not digitised.

Citation: Grattarola F, Tschernosterová K, Keil P (2024) MIAU: An analysis-ready dataset on presence-only and presence-absence data of Neotropical carnivores (Mammalia, Carnivora) from 2000 to 2021; Zenodo; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14278694>. [Dataset].

If you use our underlying data, please cite the source data as well.

Licence: Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence CC-BY 4.0 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode.en>).

3) Extended Data: the code we used to process the data.

Quarto files

- ``sources_species_and_countries.qmd``: an overview of the different sources, carnivore species and countries considered in the study.
- ``presence-absence.qmd``: an overview of the presence-absence records in the database, including the geographic, taxonomic and temporal coverage of the data.
- ``presence-only.qmd``: an overview of the presence-only records in the database, including the geographic, taxonomic and temporal coverage of the data.
- ``analysis_ready_data.qmd``: a full descriptive code to reproduce the generation of ``PO.gpk`` and ``PA.gpk``.

Citation: Grattarola F, Tschernosterová K, Keil P (2024) MIAU: An analysis-ready dataset on presence-only and presence-absence data of Neotropical carnivores (Mammalia, Carnivora) from 2000 to 2021; Zenodo; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14278694>. [Code].

Licence: Code is available under the terms of the GPL-3.0 licence (<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.html>).

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

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Author contributions

FG conceptualised the work, designed the methodology, implemented the computer code, did the data standardisation and validation, prepared the data visualisation, supervised the data digitisation work and wrote the original draft. Literature data collation and digitisation was led by KT. FG and PK did the project administration. PK acquired funding. FG, KT and PK reviewed and edited the manuscript. The authors' contributions to the scholarly output followed the 'Contributor Roles Taxonomy' (CRediT; <https://credit.niso.org/>).

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Complete list of the 64 digitised literature sources

Authors: Florencia Grattarola, Kateřina Tschernosterová, Petr Keil

Data type: csv

Explanation note: See <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14278694> for a BibTeX with the bibliographical database file.

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Supplementary material 2

Supplementary information

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Data type: docx

Explanation note: **table S2**. Density of presence-only (PO) and presence-absence (PA) surveys per country. **figure S1**. Number of presence-only (PO) and presence-absence (PA) records per country and density of records and surveys per area (1/1,000 km²).

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